

MPowerBIO

eM-POWERing SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death

D7.2 Data Management Plan

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Participant No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country	Organisation type
1	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark http://foodbiocluster.dk/	FBCD	DK	Non-profit SME/Cluster
2	TechTour Global https://www.techtour.com/	TTG	BG	SME
3	CLIB https://www.clib2021.de/	CLIB	DE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
4	Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/	CTA	ES	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
5	Italbiotec https://www.italbiotec.it/	IBT	IT	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
6	FoodScale Hub https://foodscalehub.com/	FSH	RS	Non-profit Association /Cluster
7	EIT Food https://www.eitfood.eu/	EIT	BE	Non-profit Association
8	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/	IBF	IE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
9	Q-Plan International https://qplan-intl.gr/	QPL	GR	SME
10	Sustainable Innovations Europe https://www.sustainableinnovations.eu/	SIE	ES	SME

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1. Executive summary

This plan is based on the "Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP" template provided by Horizon 2020 (European Commission) within the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD pilot) conducted by the EC.

As this is a Coordination and Support Action, experimental research data will not be used, but information about cluster staff skills, training needs, investment sources and other statistical data will be retrieved. In the present project, data refers to any kind of survey results, interview recordings, images and bibliographic metadata used for the validation publications.

The consortium will have to comply with all European and national legislation and directives relevant to the country where the data collections are taking place. The collection, processing and transmission of personal data will be analysed under principles of:

- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data
- The recently published General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)
- The national laws applying its provisions.
- Any additional regulations at national level that do not fall under the GDRP and apply to data protection or any other sensitive information will also be taken into account.
- Data managed during the project will be processed only under the following preconditions that need to be met:
 - When the data subject has given her/his consent
 - When the processing is necessary for the performance of or the entering into a contract
 - When processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation
 - When processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject.

Data processing will be done in respect to the purposes for which the data were collected or for which they are further processed, while ensuring appropriate protection for personal data stored for longer periods for historical, statistical or scientific use.

2. About the Project

Many SMEs experience that even though they have a good idea or a good product, they cannot get an investor. They need to be able to pitch their idea perfectly, have a strong business plan, a clear strategy, a well-defined customer base, etc. to attract investors.

European clusters need to be better suited to help small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) overcome the valley of death i.e. the difficult task of finding sufficient investment to get from idea to business. This is the main focus of the MPowerBIO project.

In the MPowerBIO project 10 training the trainers' events will be arranged for a total of 90 clusters across the bioeconomy, covering most of Europe. The events are set up to help clusters understand how SMEs can obtain capital and grow.

Online training modules and regional trainers' events will be organised to build the capacity of clusters to train their SME members and give them the best possibilities for preparing and presenting high quality projects to investors.

The best SME projects from these events will be selected by investors, and invited to one of two European finals, At the final, the selected companies will present their ideas to a panel of investors and experts from large organisations and venture funds in Europe, with the aim of attracting capital to grow and develop their business.

A total of 72 high-quality, screened and investment-ready SMEs are expected to pitch at the two final events. The project will screen and support 250 SMEs towards this goal.

3. Data Summary

3.1. Purpose of Data Generation and Collection

Data generated and collected in the MPowerBIO project will be used to develop knowledge in order to:

- Develop a Capacity Building Programme to improve clusters ability to assess investment readiness level and support their SME members in presenting high-quality projects to investors
- Build a Business Support Programme designed to enhance investment readiness for SME's
- Map existing investment sources

3.2. Data Generation and Collection

Data gathered during the whole project are mainly structured documents and are shared by the project's participants through the platform Podio (see section 5 for more information). Survey data will not be shared among the partners but will be kept by the responsible partner together with the consent form. Only the summary and conclusions will be shared in a version that do not consist personal data.

Only non-sensitive personal data will be collected (name, contact e-mail) for statistical and dissemination purposes. Informed consent of the participants in the surveys and questionnaires will be duly provided by the WP leader with a specific template and on the actual on-line forms used to retrieve information from the relevant stakeholders.

Data will only regard the following:

- Survey activities foreseen during the project (WP1)
- Contact information for partners and participants

- Economic reporting

Data collection in Task 1.1 Mapping Existing investment sources and revealing their requirements and Task 1.2 Analysing available and missing skills to identify training needs:

- T1.1: Each partner sends the Information Sheet (Annex 1) to the interviewees and collect the signed Consent Forms (Annex 2).
- T1.2:
 - The partners interview experts to validate/revise the competence skills framework. As a first step the experts are asked to complete an online form in Goggle sheets. Followed up by an interview, they receive the Information Sheet and the partner collect the signed Consent Forms
 - The project has launched an open survey through EUSurvey.

Contact information on partners, Advisory Board and for Industry and Market Expert Group (provided by BIC) will be shared in Podio and Microsoft Teams.

Results from the skills gap analysis will be made accessible in a report and widely distributed to relevant stakeholders.

When transferring information regarding the economic report, the files are being sent through Podio to a secure workspace where only limited people in Food & Bio Cluster Denmark has access, mainly controllers.

The size of data is not expected to be large, as it only contains the data from the surveys and the economic reports from the partners.

4. Allocation of resources

All partners take responsibility for the data management in the project. The coordinator is responsible for maintaining the internal repository tool, Podio, and the updating of all documents and reports. Data transferred among team members will follow strictly the protection of personal and confidential data sets as described in this DMP. No personal data will be transferred by other platforms than Podio.

5. Data security

Security and backup of project data are granted using Podio.

Here are some key elements about security at Podio:

- Customer-uploaded data is hosted through Amazon Web Services in Dublin
- HTTPS Encryption on all data between the Podio service and the client web browser. Login with-out encryption is non-optional. Podio servers are firewalled and only those services which are required to be running are listening. Connections between servers are made using encrypted se-cure tunnels
- Podio employees do not access customer uploaded data in Podio without prior customer consent.
- No super-user account exists in the organization. All accounts are private to each individual user
- Read our privacy policy here: <https://www.citrix.com/about/legal/privacy>
- All data is backed up nightly and copied to another off-site location
- Access all your uploaded data programmatically via the Podio API: <https://developers.podio.com/>
- Multiple client libraries available
- Import/export data or connect external services to Podio via the API
- Regular security audits are carried out by internal Citrix security team
- Citrix Security Exhibit: <https://www.citrix.com/buy/licensing/citrix-services-security-exhibit.html>

Microsoft Teams enforces team-wide and organization-wide two-factor authentication, single sign-on through Active Directory, and encryption of data in transit and at rest. Files are stored in SharePoint and are backed by SharePoint encryption. Notes are stored in OneNote and are backed by OneNote encryption. The OneNote data is stored in the team SharePoint site. The Wiki tab can also be used for note taking and its content is also stored within the team SharePoint site.

Read [Identity models and authentication](#) for more insight into authentication and Teams, and [How modern authentication works](#) will help with modern authentication in particular.

Because Teams works in partnership with SharePoint, OneNote, Exchange, and more, you should be comfortable managing security in Microsoft 365 or Office 365 all-up. To learn more, read about [how to configure your Microsoft 365 or Office 365 organization for increased security](#).

Find more information here: <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoftteams/security-compliance-overview>

Podio and Teams are fully in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and Food & Bio Cluster have a Data Processing Addendum with both Podio and Microsoft Teams.

The online learning platform powering the Capacity Building Programme and the Business Support Programme is a part of MPowerBIO website and is hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS) and events Backoffice is powered by the Tech Tour event management platform. The public portal is connected to a feedback collector, which saves external feedback and support tickets in JIRA. Moodle is integrated as the online courses tool, providing the online training content prepared under WP1. Some of the courses (especially the courses designed as videos and constituting large files) are hosted on Vimeo but are accessible only for visitors coming from the MPowerBIO portal and the moodle instances and are not accessible for other visitors. Applications from SMEs are collected in a database through Cognito Forms, which syncs to a Google sheet for a better user experience, powered by Integromat.

Figure 1 MPowerBio platform overall architecture

6. Ethical aspects

The project does not foresee any particular aspects to be addressed from an ethical perspective.

Annex 1

Example of Information Sheet

MPowerBIO

Information Sheet

Mapping of existing investment resources and their characteristics

Partners

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 887501.

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www.mpowerbio.eu

Introduction

We invite you to participate in a survey that is being carried out by MPowerBIO, a project funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme. Before you decide to participate and share your personal data with us, you need to understand why we are conducting this survey and what your participation will involve. Please take the time to carefully read this information sheet and ask questions about anything you do not understand.

What is the MPowerBIO project all about?

MPowerBIO will empower 90 clusters within the bio-based industry across Europe to be better equipped to help SMEs overcome the challenge of finding sufficient investment to get from idea to business. By developing an online platform with digital tools our goal is to get 250 SMEs one step closer to capturing investment.

To enhance the investment readiness of SMEs, MPowerBIO will offer training modules for clusters to be better equipped to help the SMEs. SMEs will be offered concrete tools through this online platform, which will improve the investment readiness and pitching skills. Finally, MPowerBIO will connect SMEs and investors by arranging regional and international events where SMEs have the opportunity to pitch their business plan.

Who are the consortium partners of MPowerBIO?

This survey is conducted by the MPowerBIO consortium that consist of the following partner organisations: Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (DK - <http://foodbiocluster.dk>) (lead partner), Tech Tour Global (BG - www.techtour.com), Cluster Industrielle Biotechnologie 2021 E.V (DE - www.clib2021.de), Fundacion Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia (ES - www.corporaciontecnologica.com), Consorzio Italbiotec (IT - www.italbiotec.it), Foodscale Hub Entrepreneurship and Innovation Association (RS - www.foodscalehub.com), EIT Food (BE - <https://eit.europa.eu/eit-community/eit-food>), Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (IE - <https://bioeconomyfoundation.com>), Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (GR - <https://qplanintl.gr>) and Sustainable Innovations Europe SL. (ES - www.sustainableinnovations.co).

What is the purpose of this survey?

The aim of the survey is to identify and record the existing investment sources and better understand their particularities, requirements, and needs. This exercise and its analysis will help us to develop need-driven business support and capacity building programmes, align them with the real needs of investors and, ultimately, improve the investment readiness and pitching skills of innovators, startups and SMEs in the biobased industry

Is my participation in this survey voluntary and what does it involve?

Your participation is voluntary. If you consent to participate by being interviewed, we will ask you to sign an informed consent form and you will be given this information sheet to keep along with a copy of your signed informed consent form. During the interview, we will ask you a series of questions relevant to the purpose of this survey and collect the information you will provide us. After the interview, your involvement in the project will only be for as long as you wish. Indeed, during the project (spanning from 1st May 2020 to 31st October 2022), you may be asked to participate in

workshops and events held by MPowerBIO. You are free to decline to participate in any of these activities, as you wish.

What if I change my mind later on and want to withdraw my consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time and ask us to have the personal data we collected from you erased and no longer use it. You do not have to give us any reason for making this choice and no adverse consequences will be implied for you if you decide to do so. Should you wish to withdraw your consent, please contact and convey your request to **<MPowerBIO partner>** (the contact details are mentioned at the end of this document)

How will you process my personal data?

Your personal data will be processed in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation of the EU as well as the respective applicable national regulation(s).

We will collect your personal data through an interview. The consortium partner of MPowerBIO that interviewed you will securely store this data. It will be preserved in its records only for as long as necessary for us to comply with our contractual obligations to the funding authority of the project and no longer than 5 years from the project's completion. During this period, your personal data will be accessible only by authorised individuals of MPowerBIO's consortium partner that collected this data. After this period, your personal data will be deleted from the respective consortium partner's records. With your permission, we would like to anonymise the personal data that you will provide us for this survey, aggregate them with data collected from other interviewees participating in this survey and analyse them with the aim of serving the purpose of this survey. The anonymization and aggregation of the data will help ensure that you cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from this survey.

What are my rights in the context of my participation in this survey?

Your participation in this survey encompasses a number of rights which you can exercise at any time. In particular:

- You have the right to **be informed** about the collection and use of your personal data, including the purpose for which we are processing this data, the period that we will retain it and with whom we will share it.
- You have the right to ask from us to confirm whether we are processing personal data concerning you. If that is the case, you can **access** your personal data that we are processing (including copies of this data) and relevant supplementary information.
- You have the right to request from us **modifications** to your personal data in case you believe that this data is not up to date, complete or accurate.
- You have the right to ask us to **erase** your personal data that we are processing ('right to be forgotten').
- You have the right to request from us to **restrict the processing** of your personal data, with a view to limiting the way that we use this data.
- You have the right to ask for your personal data to be **provided back** to you or **transferred** to a third party.
- You have the right to **object** to us processing your personal data at any time for reasons related to your particular situation.

- You have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing (including profiling), which produces legal effects concerning you or similarly significantly affects you.

We will provide information on actions taken on a request upon your above rights without undue delay and in any event within one month of receipt of the request. That period may be extended by two further months if necessary, taking into account the complexity and number of your requests. We will inform you of any such extension together with the reasons for the delay.

Are there any risks involved?

There are no risks involved in this survey other than what you would encounter in daily life.

Will I benefit from this study?

By participating in this survey, you will be contributing towards the demand-driven development of MPowerBIO training programmes according to your needs and requirements. On top of that, you may get the chance to participate in future project activities, should you wish to (such e-learning courses, workshops etc.).

Who do I contact if I have a request, concern or complaint?

Any request, concern or complaint about any aspect of your experience during the course of this survey will be addressed. To this end, feel free to communicate with the partner of the MPowerBIO consortium that is conducting the survey, using the details provided below. **MPowerBIO consortium partner:** name of MPowerBIO partner **Contact person:** person responsible on behalf of MPowerBIO partner

Phone:

Email:

Website:

Please keep in mind that you have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority if you wish so. To this end, you can contact <name of the national Data Protection Authority>.

Phone:

Email:

Website:

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet!

Annex 2

Example of Consent Form

MPowerBIO

Informed Consent Form

Mapping of existing investment resources and their characteristics

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“eM-POWERing SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death” Grant Agreement No 887501

Please initial each box

I have read and understood the Information Sheet that I was provided. I have been given a full explanation of the nature, purpose, location and likely duration of my participation and of what will be expected from me in its context.

I give consent to anonymous verbatim quotations being used in reports and other publications of the project.

I understand that my personal data will be held and processed in confidence and in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council (27 April 2016), as well as with relevant national regulations and laws.

I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without the need to justify my decision.

I confirm that I have read and understood the above and freely consent to participate in the survey. I have been given adequate time to consider my participation.

Name of interviewee (*BLOCK CAPITALS*):

Signature:

Date:

Name of person receiving consent (*BLOCK CAPITALS*):

Signature:

Date:

